

Comparative Analysis of the Software Effort Estimation Models

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Abstract—Accurate software cost estimates are critical to both developers and customers. They can be used for generating request for proposals, contract negotiations, scheduling, monitoring and control. The exact relationship between the attributes of the effort estimation is difficult to establish. A neural network is good at discovering relationships and pattern in the data. So, in this paper a comparative analysis among existing Halstead Model, Walston-Felix Model, Bailey-Basili Model, Doty Model and Neural Network Based Model is performed. Neural Network has outperformed the other considered models. Hence, we proposed Neural Network system as a soft computing approach to model the effort estimation of the software systems.

Keywords—Effort Estimation, Neural Network, Halstead Model, Walston-Felix Model, Bailey-Basili Model, Doty Model.

I. INTRODUCTION

IN the last three decades, many quantitative software cost estimation models have been developed. An empirical model uses data from previous projects to evaluate the current project and derives the basic formulae from analysis of the particular database available. An analytical model, on the other hand, uses formulae based on global assumptions, such as the rate at which developer solve problems and the number of problems available. Evaluation of many software models were presented in [1], [2], [3]. Numerous models were explored to provide better effort estimation [4], [5], [6], [7]. In [8], [9], authors provided a survey on the effort and cost estimation models.

Typical major models that are being used as benchmarks for software effort estimation are:

- Halstead,
- Walston-Felix
- Bailey-Basili
- Doty (for KLOC > 9)

These models have been derived by studying large number of completed software projects from various organizations and applications to explore how project sizes mapped into project

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effort. But still these models are not able to predict the Effort Estimation accurately.

As the exact relationship between the attributes of the effort estimation is difficult to establish so a Neural Network approach could serve as an automatic tool to generate model by formulating the relationship based on its training. When one designs with Neural Networks alone, the network is a black box that needs to be defined; this is a highly compute-intensive process. One must develop a good sense, after extensive experimentation and practice, of the complexity of the network and the learning algorithm to be used.

As Neural based system is able to approximate the non-linear function with more precision and non of the researcher have explored Neuro approach for the Effort Estimation and there is still scope of exploring more statistical modeling approaches. So, in this proposed study, it is tried to use Neural Network Based Approach to build a more accurate model that can improve accuracy estimates of effort required to build a software system.

II. METHODOLOGY USED

The following steps are used for the comparative study:

A. Preliminary Study

First, Survey of the existing Models of Effort Estimation that are discussed in the literature.

B. Data Collection

Collect the historical software estimation data so that the same data can be used for experimentation evaluation.

C. Calculate Effort using Different Modes

The following models are used for the data collected in the previous step and calculate the effort for each developed model:

- Halstead,
- Walston-Felix
- Bailey-Basili
- Doty (for KLOC > 9).
- Neural Network Based System

D. Copyright Form

Perform the comparison of the models on basis of:

- Mean Magnitude of Relative Error (*MMRE*)
- Root Mean Square Error (*RMSSE*)

RMSSE is frequently used measure of differences between values predicted by a model or estimator and the

values actually observed from the thing being modeled or estimated. It is just the square root of the mean square error as shown in equation given below:

$$\sqrt{\frac{(a_1 - c_1)^2 + (a_2 - c_2)^2 + \dots + (a_n - c_n)^2}{n}} \quad (1)$$

The mean-squared error is one of the most commonly used measures of success for numeric prediction. This value is computed by taking the average of the squared differences between each computed value and its corresponding correct value. The root mean-squared error is simply the square root of the mean-squared-error.

The literature considered the mean magnitude of relative error (MMRE) as the main performance measure. The value of an effort predictor can be reported many ways including MMRE. MMRE is computed from the relative error, or RE, which is the relative size of the difference between the actual and estimated value.

Given a data set of size "D", a "Training set of size "(X=|Train|) <= D", and a "test" set of size "T=D-|Train|", then the mean magnitude of the relative error, or MMRE, is the percentage of the absolute values of the relative errors, averaged over the "T" items in the "Test" set.

In other words, *RMSSE* is frequently used measure of differences between values predicted by a model or estimator and the values actually observed from the thing being modeled or estimated. It is just the square root of the mean square error as shown in equation given below:

$$RMSSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2} \quad (2)$$

Where y_i represents the i^{th} value of the effort and \hat{y}_i is the estimated effort.

MMRE is another measure and is the percentage of the absolute values of the relative errors, averaged over the N items in the "Test" set and can be written as:

$$MMRE = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{|y_i - \hat{y}_i|}{y_i} \quad (3)$$

E. Conclusion

Deduce the conclusions of the results of the calculated errors in the previous step.

III. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

The dataset of NASA [10] is used for the comparison of different models. In this dataset, there is empirical data in terms of DKLOC, Methodology and Effort values of 18 projects as shown in Table I.

The data of first 13 projects is used as training data for the Neural Network and data of last 5 projects is used as testing data of the trained Neural Network. The neural network used is backpropagation based Neural Network that consists of two neurons in input layer, two neurons in the hidden layer and

TABLE I
 NASA DATA [10] OF EFFORT ESTIMATION

Project No.	KDLOC	Methodology	Actual Effort
1	90.2	30	115.8
2	46.2	20	96
3	46.5	19	79
4	54.5	20	90.8
5	31.1	35	39.6
6	67.5	29	98.4
7	12.8	26	18.9
8	10.5	34	10.3
9	21.5	31	28.5
10	3.1	26	7
11	4.2	19	9
12	7.8	31	7.3
13	2.1	28	5
14	5	29	8.4
15	78.6	35	98.7
16	9.7	27	15.6
17	12.5	27	23.9
18	100.8	34	138.3

one neuron in the output layer. In the testing phase the calculated efforts and errors using different models is shown in Table II and Table III respectively.

TABLE II
 ACTUAL AND CALCULATED EFFORT USING DIFFERENT EFFORT ESTIMATION MODELS

Actual Effort	NN System Effort	Halstead Model Effort	Walston-Felix Model Effort	Bailey-Basili Model Effort	Doty Model Effort
8.4	7.9455	7.8262	22.494	10.222	28.518
98.7	98.9744	487.79	275.95	120.85	510.27
15.6	14.6092	21.147	41.112	15.685	57.074
23.9	19.3829	30.936	51.783	19.169	74.431
138.3	99.5649	708.42	346.06	189.43	662.09

TABLE III
 ERRORS IN CALCULATED EFFORT USING DIFFERENT EFFORT ESTIMATION MODELS

Performance Criteria	Model Used				
	NN System	Halstead Model	Walston-Felix Model	Bailey-Basili Model	Doty Model
MMRE	11.7896	175.655	155.5596	20.2885	302.5023
RMSSE	17.4475	308.7097	123.4575	25.0224	299.4742

IV. CONCLUSION

The performance of the Neural Network based effort estimation system and the other existing Halstead Model, Walston-Felix Model, Bailey-Basili Model and Doty Model models is compared for effort dataset available in literature [10]. The results show that the Neural Network system has the lowest *MMRE* and *RMSSE* values i.e. 11.7896 and 17.4475 respectively. The second best performance is shown by Bailey-Basili software estimation system with 20.2885 and 25.0224 as *MMRE* and *RMSSE* values. Hence, the proposed Neuro based system is able to provide good estimation capabilities. It is suggested to use of Neuro based technique to build suitable generalized type of model that can be used for the software effort estimation of all types of the projects.

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